

Polarographic Behaviour of some Potential Antidiabetic Compounds with Three Reduction Sites

RAJEEV JAIN*

School of Studies in Chemistry, Jiwaji University, Gwalior-474 011

Manuscript received 8 March 1985, revised 31 October 1985, accepted 17 January 1986

The polarographic reduction of 1-(2,4-dinitrophenyl)-3,5-dimethyl-4-arylazopyrazoles takes place in three well defined reduction waves. The first two waves each 4-e at more positive potentials have been assigned to the reduction of two nitro groups, whereas the third 2-e electron wave at comparatively negative potential has been assigned to the reduction of azo group. All the three waves were found to be diffusion-controlled and irreversible. A plausible mechanism has been suggested for the reduction of azo group as evident by the number of electrons involved in the reduction and controlled potential electrolysis. The effect of substituents has been determined quantitatively by the application of Hammett equation

LITERATURE survey reveals that polarographic behaviour of 1-(2,4-dinitrophenyl)-3,5-dimethyl-4-arylazopyrazoles (1) has not been systematically studied inspite of their antidiabetic activity¹ and their unique structure from the electrochemical point of view. Keeping this in view these compounds have been studied polarographically in order to establish the preferential reduction of groups when they are present in a compound and to study the effect of substituents on the reduction of azo group.

Experimental

1 - (2,4 - Dinitrophenyl) - 3,5-dimethyl-4-arylazopyrazoles (1-14) and compounds (1a) and (1b) were synthesised by the literature method¹. Their struc-

tures were confirmed by elemental and spectral analyses. The stock solutions ($10 \times 10^{-3} M$) of all these compounds were prepared in dimethylformamide (A.R.). Britton-Robinson buffers in the pH range 2.0-11.0 were prepared in distilled water using AnalaR grade chemicals. Solutions for polarographic measurements were prepared by mixing depolariser (1.0 ml), DMF (3.0 ml) (which was necessary to prevent precipitation), 1M KCl (1.0 ml) and appropriate buffer or NaOH solution (5.0 ml). Dissolved oxygen was removed by the passage of nitrogen gas for about 15 min.

An Elico-DC CL-25 polarograph was used and the capillary characteristics were $2.10 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-2/3}$. SCE was used as the reference electrode. The number of electrons (n) involved in the reduction process was determined by the method of Devries and Kroon² and by controlled potential electrolysis. The temperature coefficient was calculated by Nejedly's method³. The uv-vis spectra of the solutions were recorded on a UV-VIS Carl Zeiss spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

In these compounds (1-14) the possible reduction sites are the cyclic C=C and C=N groups of the pyrazole ring and exocyclic N=N and NO₂ sites. As extranuclear sites are more susceptible to reduction⁴, it can be safely inferred that the reduction takes place at extranuclear N=N and NO₂ sites. This is further confirmed by the fact that simple pyrazoles are not reducible at d.m.e. under these experimental conditions whereas N=N and NO₂ groups are electroreducible.

All the compounds got precipitated in the buffered solutions of pH 2.0-11.0 and in acidic

medium. Therefore, studies were carried out in solutions of different strengths of NaOH. In these solutions all the compounds gave three well defined reduction waves. First, two reduction waves at more positive potential were found to be 4-e reduction waves whereas third wave was found to involve only 2-e in the electrode process. On the basis of number of electrons involved in the process as well as on the known easy reducibility of nitro group⁵ in both aliphatic and aromatic compounds at the d.m.e., first two waves have been assigned to the reduction of nitro groups and the third wave to the reduction of azo group. This fact was verified by synthesising a similar compound 1-phenyl-3,5-dimethyl-4-arylazopyrazole (1a) which is not having nitro groups in the phenyl ring attached to N-atom of the pyrazole nucleus. This compound was found to give only one 2-e wave at a half-wave potential corresponding to the $E_{1/2}$ of the third wave under similar experimental conditions. This fact was further confirmed by carrying out controlled potential electrolysis on the potential corresponding to the plateau of the second wave, i.e., wave for the reduction of nitro group. After controlled potential electrolysis for about ~12 h, the catholyte was subjected to product analysis. The catholyte was found not having any nitro group by the usual group tests and also on polarographic examination it did not give first two waves for the reduction of nitro groups but it gave only one wave corresponding to the potential of the third wave, which can be safely assigned to the reduction of azo group. These experiments are sufficient evidences to support that first two waves are for the reduction of nitro groups.

Reduction of nitro groups: Out of the two 4-e waves, first wave has been assigned to the reduction of NO_2 group present at 2-position in the phenyl ring whereas second wave to the reduction of 4- NO_2 group. For confirming the prior reduction of 2-nitro group, a compound 1-(4-nitrophenyl)-3,5-dimethyl-4-arylazopyrazole (1b) having only one nitro group at *para*-position was synthesised. On polarographic studies in similar experimental conditions it gave only two waves, i.e. 4-e wave for the reduction of NO_2 group at potential corresponding to the 4- NO_2 group in case of compound 1 and second 2-e wave corresponding to wave for azo group. Both the waves for the reduction of nitro groups were diffusion-controlled and irreversible⁶. The values of i_a/C and αn_a are practically independent of concentration of depolariser. A mechanism for the reduction of nitro group, similar to that suggested by other workers^{5,7-9}, can be proposed for these compounds.

Reduction of azo group: All the arylazopyrazoles (Table 1) gave a single 2-e transfer, well defined cathodic waves in different strengths of NaOH solutions. The wave was found to be diffusion-controlled and irreversible by the usual polarographic experiments. Following $(e, \text{H}^+, e, \text{H}^+)$ mechanism for the reduction of azo group based

on the number of electrons involved in the reduction and independence of $E_{1/2}$ on the strength of NaOH solutions, may be proposed for these compounds.

The controlled potential electrolysis results confirm the formation of hydrazono compound. This mechanism is further supported by the work of others on azo compounds¹¹⁻¹⁴. The maximum absorption in uv-vis spectra of 1 at 405 nm disappeared in solutions after complete electrolysis. Furthermore, the above electrolysed solution did not give any polarographic wave, thereby confirming the above reduction mechanism.

Fig. 1. Plot of $-E_{1/2}$ vs σ for 1-(2,4-dinitrophenyl)-3,5-dimethyl-4-arylazopyrazoles in 0.01 N NaOH (concn. = 1.0×10^{-4} M).

Effect of substituents: In order to express the effect of substituents quantitatively^{15,16} the $E_{1/2}$ of these arylazopyrazoles were plotted against Hammett substituent constants (σ). A linear relationship was obtained only for *meta*- and *para*-derivatives while the *ortho*-derivatives deviate significantly from the linear plot. The specific reaction constant (ρ) was found to be 0.12 V and its positive sign indicated¹⁷ the nucleophilic nature of the electrode process. The observed linear relationship of $E_{1/2}$ vs σ indicated that the substituents appreciably affected the reduction of azo group by polar and mesomeric effects through the benzene ring. For the *ortho*-derivatives, the corrected values of $E_{1/2}$ were obtained from the relationship given by Zuman¹⁵. The plot of corrected $E_{1/2}$ vs σ was linear from which the

TABLE I—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF SOME 1-(2,4-DINITROPHENYL)-3,5-DIMETHYL-4-ARYLAZOPYRAZOLES IN 0.01 N NaOH (CONCN. = 1.0×10^{-4} M)

Compd. no.	R	$-E_{1/2}$ V	i_d μA	α_n	I	$\Delta E_{1/2}$ *
1	H	1. 0.49	0.81	0.60	0.38	-
		2. 0.67	0.85	0.67	0.40	
		3. 1.05	0.40	0.30	0.19	
2	2-CH ₃	1. 0.51	0.75	0.54	0.35	0.01
		2. 0.72	0.70	0.54	0.33	
		3. 1.04	0.40	0.30	0.19	
3	3-CH ₃	1. 0.49	0.75	0.57	0.36	0.02
		2. 0.69	0.70	0.57	0.36	
		3. 1.07	0.35	0.30	0.16	
4	4-CH ₃	1. 0.48	0.80	0.55	0.38	0.03
		2. 0.69	0.75	0.57	0.36	
		3. 1.08	0.45	0.32	0.21	
5	2-Cl	1. 0.55	0.75	0.55	0.36	0.08
		2. 0.66	0.80	0.57	0.38	
		3. 0.97	0.40	0.35	0.19	
6	3-Cl	1. 0.57	0.76	0.59	0.36	0.05
		2. 0.65	0.76	0.51	0.36	
		3. 1.00	0.40	0.31	0.19	
7	4-Cl	1. 0.50	0.78	0.49	0.37	0.01
		2. 0.67	0.80	0.49	0.38	
		3. 1.04	0.45	0.27	0.21	
8	2-OC ₂ H ₅ **	1. 0.48	0.60	0.41	0.28	0.02
		2. 0.69	0.65	0.49	0.31	
		3. 1.07	0.25	0.21	0.12	
9	4-OC ₂ H ₅	1. 0.56	0.75	0.55	0.36	0.03
		2. 0.66	0.70	0.54	0.33	
		3. 1.08	0.35	0.39	0.17	
10	2-OCH ₃	1. 0.50	0.70	0.60	0.33	0.01
		2. 0.72	0.75	0.55	0.36	
		3. 1.04	0.40	0.35	0.19	
11	4-OCH ₃	1. 1.52	0.75	0.60	0.35	0.05
		2. 0.71	0.82	0.67	0.67	
		3. 1.10	0.40	0.41	0.19	
12	4-Br	1. 0.49	0.86	0.54	0.41	0.03
		2. 0.66	0.80	0.54	0.38	
		3. 1.02	0.45	0.39	0.21	
13	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂ **	1. 0.51	0.62	0.45	0.29	0.00
		2. 0.71	0.58	0.49	0.28	
		3. 1.05	0.20	0.28	0.09	
14	3,5-(CH ₃) ₂	1. 0.48	0.68	0.50	0.32	0.01
		2. 0.65	0.65	0.52	0.31	
		3. 1.06	0.30	0.27	0.14	

*For reduction of azo group. **Slight precipitation occurred.

specific reaction constant (ρ) was found to be 0.11 V, which is in good agreement with the values reported in the literature¹⁸ for similar systems. In the case of nitro group reduction, the substituents are remote from the reduction site and hence, no systematic change in $E_{1/2}$ was observed. Polarographic *ortho*-shift (ΔO) was determined for methyl, methoxy, chloro and ethoxy groups and found to be positive indicating that *ortho*-derivatives are reduced at less negative potential than their *para*-analogues.

The $E_{1/2}$ values of disubstituted compounds indicated that the 2,4-disubstituted derivative does not follow the additivity principle¹⁹, whereas the 3,5-disubstituted derivative show a reasonable additivity of 3 and 5 shifts. The smaller shift of 0.02 V in the case of *ortho*-derivatives may be attributed to the steric hindrance to coplanarity²⁰.

References

- H. G. GARG and P. P. SINGH, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1968, 11, 1103.
- T. DEVRIES and J. L. KROON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 2484.
- V. NEJEDLY, *Collect. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1929, 1, 319.
- W. U. MALIK, V. K. MAHESH and R. N. GOYAL, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1974, 54, 411.
- M. FIELDS, C. VALE, JR. and M. KANE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 42.
- L. MEITES, "Polarographic Techniques", Interscience, New York, 1967.
- M. HEYROVSKY, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1972, 36, 203.
- M. SINGH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, 60, 737.
- J. PEARSON, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1948, 44, 683.
- A. J. BARD and H. LUND, "Encyclopedia of the Electrochemistry of the Elements", Marcel Dekker, New York, 1973, Vol. XIII.
- C. R. CASTOR and H. J. SAYLOR, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 1427.
- P. J. HILSON and P. P. BIRNBAUN, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1952, 48, 478.
- B. NYGARD, *Arkiv Kemi*, 1966, 26, 167.
- I. M. ISSA, R. M. ISSA, Y. M. TEMERK and M. R. MAKMOUD, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1973, 18, 139.
- P. ZUMAN, "Substituent Effects in Organic Polarography", Plenum Press, New York, 1967.
- K. ZUTSHI, G. E. RYSCHKEWITSCH and P. ZUMAN, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1983, 22, 564.
- P. ZUMAN, *Collect. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1960, 25, 3225.
- H. H. JAFFE, *Chem. Rev.*, 1953, 53, 191.
- R. W. BROOKMAN and D. E. PEARSON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 4128.
- M. CHARTON and B. I. CHARTON, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1971, 36, 260.